

SITE SPHINX	DATE 18/VIII/80	AREA T RUMP LEDGE	SQUARE	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates: See 1:50 Rump Ledge plan		Levels	
			Top: See Section 16	Bottom:
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter:	Width: 20 cm as cleared	Length: 30 cm	Depth: 30-40 cm	

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions			
①	LOOSE SAND, RUBBLE	BUFF	LOOSE	SAND IS FINE, Limestone, mortar frags. scattered - LOOSE	T	Lm	✓ Chips, Frags	Gp	✓ Mortar
					3	Gr	✓ 3 small chips	Char	1 small piece
					Small Frags	Do			
					D	Ba			
					0	Al			
						Other	MOP CEMENT FRAGS, MANURE BITS		
②	HARD MORTAR LIMESTONE CHIPS ON LARGE STONE SLAB BOTTOM	Light whitish buff	HARD	FINE (Matrix) after Removal	T	Lm	✓ Frags.	Gp	
					1	Gr		Char	
					tiny frag.	Do			
					D	Ba			
						Al			
						Other			
②a	CLEAN SAND	TAN	LOOSE	FINE	T	Lm		Gp	
						Gr		Char	✓ 3 small pieces
						Do			
					D	Ba			
						Al			
						Other	MOP cement Frags		
○					T	Lm		Gp	
						Gr		Char	
						Do			
					D	Ba			
						Al			
						Other			
○					T	Lm		Gp	
						Gr		Char	
						Do			
					D	Ba			
						Al			
						Other			

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/ 18 No. 1 / 1	B&W: Roll/ 15 No. 1 / 1
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DRAWN	Area Plan:	Feature Plan: 1:50 Rump Ledge	Sections: stonework Section 16
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: Td3 space between restoration slab (inner period) and core projection down to underlying restoration slab of same phase while fill showing in section likely undisturbed original ① and ② contaminated w/ cement frags forced in from 1926 cement fill against S face of core projection and narrow space forming E end of Td3.

② likely original dumped mortar-limestone chips adhering to surface underlying slab.